

An Overview of Challenging Topics in AI for Trust and Security

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This short paper highlights the challenges in trustworthy AI for critical security domains, building on the scientific roadmap of the Cluster SequoIA, standing for “security, confidence, AI”, an excellence centre in AI labelled by the French national strategy on AI. The overall goal of the Cluster SequoIA, federating higher education and research (HER) institutions under the leadership of the Université de Rennes, is to promote research, education and innovation on the general theme of AI for trust and security in and by digital systems. In particular, the scientific roadmap, combined with an innovation strategy based on a strong synergy between the HER institutions of the consortium and a large set of partners, mostly private sector companies and national agencies, significantly contributes to accelerating the diffusion of AI technology in priority domains such as cybersecurity¹.

The vision of the Cluster SequoIA lies in the definition of well-understood, mastered and accepted AI solutions that address the general challenge of trust and security by and in digital systems, with a particular focus on cybersecurity, defence and environmental security. This vision encompasses an interdisciplinary perspective, ranging from fundamental challenges in trustworthy AI science to applied AI in key domains – cybersecurity, environmental observation, intelligence – and human and social research on usage, acceptability, regulation, or social transformation. This vision translates into

a number of scientific challenges schematically articulated around three pillars briefly detailed hereunder from an informatics science standpoint.

First, the *core AI* pillar addresses the foundations of trustworthy machine learning (ML), with challenges in secure, frugal, embedded, hybrid and explainable AI. From a theoretical standpoint, a better understanding of the empirical success of recent neural architectures in many domains, better formalizing the necessary conditions for a model to successfully learn and/or infer trustworthy knowledge on unseen data, e.g., by defining statistical bounds [1], is paramount. Similarly, progress is required in the design of learning procedures where data are rare or even absent in the long-tailed distributions [2] – e.g., as in novel cybersecurity attacks or extreme climate events – and in the construction of lifelong learning systems that adapt to changes in data distributions [3], including conceptual drifts, noise and outliers, and ill-specified learning sets. Formal assessment of machine learning also constitutes a raising fundamental challenge in trustworthy AI: This is a new frontier for formal methods and model checking, that drastically need adaptation of existing tools [4] to assess the robustness of general classifiers [5]. Finally, hybrid AI models, harnessing common-sense and interpretable knowledge representation with the power of data-driven machine learning

¹ A detailed version of the scientific roadmap and more information on the consortium, the partners and the

actions supported can be found at <https://cluster-sequoia.univ-rennes.fr/>.

and multi-agent systems, are also instrumental to improve trustworthy AI systems and their adoption. Yet, opening the “black-box” of machine learning raise challenges to handle and quantify uncertainty, provide human control on the system design and operation. The recent raise of LLM-based multi-agent systems offer tremendous opportunities in this direction, yet raising concerns to address regarding their controllability.

The second pillar addresses *AI, cybersecurity and defence*, with noteworthy applications in the security of systems, infrastructures, and information. Many challenges appear in the security and audit of AI systems and, in a dual manner, in the field of cybersecurity. On the first aspect, vulnerabilities of ML models arise at both learning and inference stages [6], and current approaches are mostly based on oversimplified scenarios considering a static ML pipeline: The risk of attacks already existing in training and inference – adversarial evasion [7], data poisoning and data attacks [8] – is thus underestimated as the potential attack surface extends in real-world AI systems. We advocate for a paradigm shift to secure AI systems at scale, better characterising the roots of the vulnerabilities, shifting from model to system security, encompassing hardware issues and the full life-cycle of dynamical AI systems. In the field of cybersecurity, AI-based approaches to core cybersecurity tasks – e.g., detection of vulnerabilities and intrusions – remain a challenge due to the complex nature of the data and the specifics of the events to detect [9, 10], requiring specific models and realistic data that are still in infancy. A different approach lies in the optimal and dynamic deployment of AI-based security policies according to operational constraints or under attack, leveraging LLMs and their extension to agentic AI systems. These models are, however, also used to lower the cost of attacks, as evidenced by the recent controversy on Claude Mythos, challenging cybersecurity in a way that is yet to be fully apprehended. Lastly, information security is also

being challenged by generative AI [11], calling for clear solutions, e.g., to track and characterise content and models, and facilitate fact-checking: watermarking content and models at scale, auditing LLMs for factual behaviour, or combining ML with knowledge-based reasoning are key research.

Finally, the third pillar focuses on *AI, environment and ocean*, focusing on the observation and modelling of the earth’s systems to address societal and scientific challenges on environmental security, climate change, and underwater defence. Many core ML challenges from the first pillar straightforwardly extend to the observation and modelling of complex systems such as the Earth or the ocean. Very large-scale, possibly chaotic, systems involving global physical equilibrium, however, require suitable AI frameworks to establish surrogate data-driven physical models [12]. Such systems remain highly sensitive to uncertainties in initial conditions and errors in training samples. They require better statistical robustness of predictions and the assessment of confidence intervals, e.g., leveraging conformal prediction [13] and bridging variational data assimilation, meta-learning and uncertainty quantification [14]. Also, integrating heterogeneous and noisy data acquired from diverse sensors [15] with multiple spatial and temporal resolutions remains a challenge for today’s ML paradigms, calling for new approaches and foundation models. Remote sensing also features challenges in the detection and identification of weak signals and abnormal behaviour, sharing common fundamental issues with cybersecurity that deviate from mere statistical modelling and require embedding knowledge – physical priors, ontologies – into AI models [16].

As highlighted, the three pillars are strongly intertwined, with core AI challenges that arise from and drive research in the application areas. They also need to rely on transversal research that spans all pillars. On the technology side, continuum computing is a key enabler, with

specific hardware and embedded AI systems – that raise new security threats – to HPC frameworks for efficient and as frugal as possible data processing and machine learning. Continuous integration and test in AI system deployment, known as MLOps, is also a new challenge facing security, stability and backward compatibility issues. But the main transversal research topics are non-technical and relate to usage at large. We argue that, in critical domains such as cybersecurity or defence, AI technologies should be at the service of users, ultimately responsible for the decisions and actions they take. Users' perception and appropriation of AI-based technology must be addressed through real-life user studies encompassing most of these aspects. Involving ethical factors (bias, application autonomy) and legal aspects right from the design stage rises important

challenges [17, 18]. It is also important to reinforce and adapt the legal framework driving usage, taking into account *lato sensu* users – individuals, professionals, companies, administrations and, broadly, any human organisation [19] – and the central question of AI responsibility [20].

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